

Supplementary document to the paper “Optimal Bidding of Flexible Demand in Electricity Markets with Block Orders”

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NOMENCLATURE

A. Indices and Sets

$t \in T$	Index and set of time periods
w	Index of steps of operational cycle of flexible demand with fixed power
l	Index of power levels of flexible demand with discretely adjustable power
Y^{OPRT}	Set of operational constraints of flexible demand

B. Parameters and Functions

E	Daily energy requirement of flexible demand (MWh)
$t^{\text{IN}}, t^{\text{TER}}$	Earliest acceptable initiation time and latest acceptable termination time of flexible demand
$t^{\text{B1}}, t^{\text{B2}}$	Preferred / baseline initiation and termination times of flexible demand
T^{DUR}	Duration of cycle of flexible demand with fixed power (h)
C^-, C^+	Marginal inconvenience cost of flexible demand for earlier and later operation (£/h)
C^0	Cost of forgoing the operation of flexible demand (£)
D_w^{CYC}	Power consumption of flexible demand with fixed power, at cycle step w (MW)
D_l^{LVL}	Power consumption of flexible demand with discretely adjustable power, at power level l (MW)
$D^{\text{min}}, D^{\text{max}}$	Minimum and maximum power consumption of flexible demand with continuously adjustable power (MW)

C. Variables

d_t	Power consumption of flexible demand at period t (MW)
c^{INC}	Inconvenience cost of flexible demand (£)
c^{FOR}	Forgoing cost of flexible demand (£)
y_t^{IN}	Binary variable expressing whether flexible demand is initiated at the beginning of period t (1) or not (0)
y_t^{TER}	Binary variable expressing whether flexible demand is terminated at the beginning of period t (1) or not (0)

$u_{t,l}^{\text{LVL}}$	Binary variable indicating whether flexible demand at period t , is operated at power level l (1) or not (0)
u_t^{ON}	Binary variable expressing whether flexible demand is operating at period t (1) or not (0)
δ^-	Temporal extent of earlier initiation of flexible demand (h)
δ^+	Temporal extent of later termination of flexible demand (h)

I. INTRODUCTION TO THE CONTENT OF THE SUPPLEMENTARY DOCUMENT

This supplementary document presents the operational models of the different types of flexible demand (FD) examined in our paper. According to the main body of the paper (Section I-A), the notion of flexible demand (FD) involves two distinct flexibility potentials: a) the ability to completely forgo planned demand activities, and b) the ability to temporally re-distribute demand activities. Furthermore, the second flexibility potential is much more promising in real applications, as its implications on the consumers’ utility are much lower.

In this context, although the examined operational models by no means capture the huge diversity of existing FD technologies, they account for both above flexibility potentials. In order to capture the different implications of the two potentials on the consumers’ utility, we differentiate the cost (or disutility) associated with forgoing demand activities (which we denote as forgoing cost c^{FOR}) and the cost (or disutility) associated with temporally re-distributing demand activities (which we denote as inconvenience cost c^{INC}), with the former being significantly higher than the latter.

Going further, we examine three different types of FD, according to their capability to adjust their power levels: 1) FD with fixed power, 2) FD with discretely adjustable power, and 3) FD with continuously adjustable power. The formulation of the set of operational constraints Y^{OPRT} , the forgoing cost c^{FOR} , and the inconvenience cost c^{INC} for each of these types is presented in the following sections II-IV. These formulations are generally based on previous work [1]–[4]. Without loss of generality, we assume that all three types are non-interruptible, i.e., if they are activated and start consuming power, they cannot be interrupted until they acquire the total energy required for their operation.

Finally, Section V of this supplementary document provides the assumed values of the parameters of these operational models, used in the case studies of the main body of the paper.

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Fig. 1. Types of FD considered in this paper.

II. FD WITH FIXED POWER

The first type of flexible loads is the least flexible out of the three examined types, since their power consumption profile is fixed (D_w^{CYC} for each step w of their operational cycle) and cannot be modified (and thus the duration of their cycle T^{DUR} is also fixed). Therefore, their temporal redistribution flexibility lies only in their ability to shift their whole power profile earlier or later in time, as long as this is done within an acceptable (by their users) temporal interval, denoted as $[t^{IN}, t^{TER}]$. This flexibility is illustrated in Fig. 1a, where different curves correspond to different feasible options regarding their operation: i) the red curve corresponds to the preferred / baseline operation option (with the relevant baseline interval denoted as $[t^{B1}, t^{B2}]$), i.e., the one that does not yield an inconvenience cost to the users, ii) the blue curve corresponds to an earlier operation option (with relevant inconvenience cost), and iii) the green curve corresponds to a later operation option (again with relevant inconvenience cost). The operational model of this type is formulated as follows:

$$Y^{OPRT} = \left\{ \sum_{t < t^{IN}} y_t^{IN} = 0, \quad \sum_{t > t^{TER} - T^{DUR} + 1} y_t^{IN} = 0, \quad (1) \right.$$

$$\left. \sum_{t^{IN}}^{t^{TER} - T^{DUR} + 1} y_t^{IN} \leq 1, \quad (2) \right.$$

$$d_t = \sum_{w=1}^{w=T^{DUR}} y_{t+1-w}^{IN} \cdot D_w^{CYC}, \quad \forall t, \quad (3)$$

$$\delta^- = \sum_{y=0}^{y=t^{B1}-t^{IN}} \left[\underbrace{\sum_t y_t^{IN}}_{\substack{\text{1 if not} \\ \text{forgone}}} - \underbrace{\sum_{x=0}^{x=y} y_{t^{B1}-x}^{IN}}_{\substack{\text{1 if initiated} \\ \text{in } [t^{B1}-y, t^{B1}]} } - \underbrace{\sum_{o=t^{B1}+1}^{o=t^{TER}-T^{DUR}+1} y_o^{IN}}_{\substack{\text{1 if initiated} \\ \text{later than } t^{B1}}} \right], \quad (4)$$

$$\delta^+ = \sum_{y=t^{TER}-T^{DUR}+1}^{y=t^{TER}} \left[\underbrace{\sum_t y_t^{IN}}_{\substack{\text{1 if not} \\ \text{forgone}}} - \underbrace{\sum_{x=t^{B1}}^{x=y} y_x^{IN}}_{\substack{\text{1 if initiated} \\ \text{in } [t^{B1}, y]}} - \underbrace{\sum_{o=t^{IN}}^{o=t^{B1}-1} y_o^{IN}}_{\substack{\text{1 if initiated} \\ \text{earlier than } t^{B1}}} \right], \quad (5)$$

$$c^{INC} = C^- \cdot \delta^- + C^+ \cdot \delta^+, \quad (6)$$

$$c^{FOR} = C^0 \cdot \left(1 - \sum_t y_t^{IN} \right), \quad (7)$$

where $\{d_t, \delta^-, \delta^+, c^{INC}, c^{FOR}\} \geq 0$ and $y_t^{IN} \in \{0, 1\}$. The primary decision variables of the model are the binary variables y_t^{IN} , indicating whether the load is initiated at the beginning of period t ($y_t^{IN} = 1$) or not ($y_t^{IN} = 0$). Constraints (1) enforce that the load cannot operate outside the acceptable temporal interval i.e., before the earliest initiation time and after the latest termination time. Constraint (2) ensures that the load can be operated at maximum once during the acceptable interval (or never if we decide to forgo the relevant demand activity). Constraints (3) determine the power consumption of the load at each time period, as a function of the primary decision variables y_t^{IN} . Constraints (4) / (5) determine the temporal extents of earlier initiation / later termination (with respect to the preferred initiation / termination times), also as functions of the primary decision variables y_t^{IN} ; note that only one of these temporal extents can be positive in any feasible solution. Constraint (6) defines the total inconvenience cost, which is proportional to the temporal extents of earlier initiation and later termination; specifically, for each hour of earlier initiation, the FD participant incurs a marginal inconvenience cost of C^- (£/h), while for each hour of later termination, the FD participant incurs a marginal inconvenience cost of C^+ (£/h). Constraint (7) defines the forgoing cost, which is only incurred if the load is not initiated at any time.

III. FD WITH DISCRETELY ADJUSTABLE POWER

The second type of flexible loads is more flexible than the first type above, in that their power can be adjusted. However, this additional flexibility is subject to two conditions: a) their total energy consumption within the acceptable temporal interval is fixed and cannot be modified (unless the relevant demand activity is forgone, in which case their total energy consumption is zero), and b) their power adjustability involves a finite set of discrete power levels D_l^{LVL} , i.e., their power cannot be continuously adjusted. Their flexibility is illustrated in Fig. 1b, and their operational model is formulated as follows:

$$Y^{OPRT} = \left\{ \sum_{t < t^{IN}} u_{t,l}^{LVL} = 0, \quad \sum_{t > t^{TER}} u_{t,l}^{LVL} = 0, \quad \forall l, \quad (8) \right.$$

$$\left. \sum_l u_{t,l}^{LVL} \leq 1, \quad \forall t, \quad (9) \right.$$

$$\sum_t y_t^{IN} \leq 1, \quad \sum_t y_t^{TER} \leq 1, \quad (10)$$

$$y_t^{IN} + y_t^{TER} \leq 1, \quad \forall t, \quad (11)$$

$$y_t^{IN} - y_t^{TER} = \sum_l u_{t,l}^{LVL} - \sum_l u_{t-1,l}^{LVL}, \quad \forall t, \quad (12)$$

$$d_t = \sum_l u_{t,l}^{\text{LVL}} \cdot D_l^{\text{LVL}}, \quad \forall t, \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{t^{\text{IN}}}^{t^{\text{TER}}} d_t = E \cdot \sum_t y_t^{\text{IN}}, \quad (14)$$

$$\delta^- = \sum_{y=0}^{y=t^{\text{B1}}-t^{\text{IN}}} \left[\overbrace{\sum_t y_t^{\text{IN}}}^{\text{1 if not forgone}} - \overbrace{\sum_{x=0}^{x=y} y_{t^{\text{B1}}-x}^{\text{IN}}}^{\text{1 if initiated in } [t^{\text{B1}}-y, t^{\text{B1}}]} - \overbrace{\sum_{o=t^{\text{B1}}+1}^{o=t^{\text{TER}}} y_o^{\text{IN}}}^{\text{1 if initiated later than } t^{\text{B1}}} \right], \quad (15)$$

$$\delta^+ = \sum_{y=t^{\text{B2}}}^{y=t^{\text{TER}}} \left[\overbrace{\sum_t y_t^{\text{IN}}}^{\text{1 if not forgone}} - \overbrace{\sum_{x=t^{\text{B2}}}^{x=y} y_{x+1}^{\text{TER}}}^{\text{1 if terminated in } [t^{\text{B2}}+1, t^{\text{TER}}+1]} - \overbrace{\sum_{o=t^{\text{IN}}}^{o=t^{\text{B2}}-1} y_{o+1}^{\text{TER}}}^{\text{1 if terminated earlier than } t^{\text{B2}}+1} \right], \quad (16)$$

(6), (7) },

where $\{u_{t,l}^{\text{LVL}}, y_t^{\text{TER}}\} \in \{0, 1\}$. The primary decision variables of the model are the binary variables $u_{t,l}^{\text{LVL}}$ indicating whether the load operates at the power level l during period t ($u_{t,l}^{\text{LVL}} = 1$) or not ($u_{t,l}^{\text{LVL}} = 0$) as well as the binary variables $y_t^{\text{IN}} / y_t^{\text{TER}}$, indicating whether the load is initiated / terminated at the beginning of period t ($y_t^{\text{IN}} = 1 / y_t^{\text{TER}} = 1$) or not ($y_t^{\text{IN}} = 0 / y_t^{\text{TER}} = 0$). Constraints (8) enforce that the load cannot operate outside the acceptable temporal interval. Constraints (9) express that the load can operate at (maximum) one of the alternative discrete power levels, during each period of the acceptable interval. Constraints (10) ensure that the load can be operated at maximum once during the acceptable interval (or never if we decide to forgo the relevant demand activity). Constraints (11)-(12) orchestrate the necessary relations between the different binary variables of the model, following the logic of typical unit commitment constraints [5]. Constraints (13) determine the power consumption of the load at each time period, as a function of the decision variables $u_{t,l}^{\text{LVL}}$. Constraints (14) ensure that the total energy consumption within the acceptable interval is either zero (if the relevant demand activity is forgone) or equal to the fixed energy requirement of the load (E). Constraints (15) / (16) are similar to constraints (4) / (5) and determine the temporal extents of earlier initiation / later termination. The inconvenience cost and forgoing cost are defined in an identical fashion with the first type examined in the previous section (6)-(7).

IV. FD WITH CONTINUOUSLY ADJUSTABLE POWER

The third type of flexible loads is more flexible than the second type above, in that their power adjustability is continuous, i.e., their power can take any value between a minimum limit D^{min} and a maximum limit D^{max} . However, their flexibility is still subject to the condition of fixed total energy consumption within the acceptable interval (unless the relevant demand activity is forgone, in which case their total energy consumption is zero). Their flexibility is illustrated in Fig. 1c, and their operational model is formulated as follows:

$$Y^{\text{OPRT}} = \left\{ \sum_{t < t^{\text{IN}}} u_t^{\text{ON}} = 0, \sum_{t > t^{\text{TER}}} u_t^{\text{ON}} = 0, \right. \quad (17)$$

$$u_t^{\text{ON}} \cdot D^{\text{min}} \leq d_t \leq u_t^{\text{ON}} \cdot D^{\text{max}}, \quad \forall t, \quad (18)$$

$$y_t^{\text{IN}} - y_t^{\text{TER}} = u_t^{\text{ON}} - u_{t-1}^{\text{ON}}, \quad \forall t, \quad (19)$$

(6), (7), (10), (11), (14) – (16) }.

where $\{u_t^{\text{ON}}\} \in \{0, 1\}$. The primary decision variables of the model are the binary variables u_t^{ON} , indicating whether the load operates at period t ($u_t^{\text{ON}} = 1$) or not ($u_t^{\text{ON}} = 0$), the binary variables $y_t^{\text{IN}} / y_t^{\text{TER}}$ (defined as in the previous section), and the continuous variables d_t . Constraints (17) enforce that the load cannot operate outside the acceptable temporal interval. Constraints (18) impose the minimum and maximum power limits. Constraints (19) are similar to constraints (12) and orchestrate the necessary relations between the different binary variables of the model.

V. ASSUMED VALUES OF PARAMETERS IN THE CASE STUDIES OF THE PAPER

The assumed values of the operational parameters that are common for all three types are as follows: $E = 1850\text{MWh}$, $[t^{\text{IN}}, t^{\text{TER}}] = [6, 22]$, $[t^{\text{B1}}, t^{\text{B2}}] = [12, 15]$, $C^- = C^+ = 4, 000$ £/h, $C^0 = \text{£}600,000$, and the preferred / baseline operation profile is $d_{12} = 250\text{MW}$, $d_{13} = 550\text{MW}$, $d_{14} = 700\text{MW}$, and $d_{15} = 350\text{MW}$. As discussed in the beginning of this supplementary document, the three types differ with respect to their capability to adjust their power levels. In this context, and in order to render comparable the examined cases with different types, we assume: a) $T^{\text{DUR}} = 4$ and $D_1^{\text{CYC}}, D_2^{\text{CYC}}, D_3^{\text{CYC}}, D_4^{\text{CYC}} = 250, 550, 700, 350$ MW for the FD with fixed power, b) $D_1^{\text{LVL}}, D_2^{\text{LVL}}, D_3^{\text{LVL}}, D_4^{\text{LVL}} = 250, 550, 700, 350$ MW for the FD with discretely adjustable power, and c) $D^{\text{min}} = 250$ MW and $D^{\text{max}} = 700$ MW for the FD with continuously adjustable power.

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